

A STUDY ON CONSTRAINTS ASSOCIATED WITH FOOD WASTE AT HOUSEHOLD LEVEL*

BY

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Abstract

Food is the very limited resources on the earth; it is the requirement of each and every creature in the universe. No creature can live without food. World is facing the major issue of managing food waste. Wastage of food occurs from starting stage to consumption stage (domestic level). Food waste at domestic level is the common but serious problem that everyone comes across. Before identifying the solution, it is important to find out the route of the problem. This research paper is focused on identifying the route (reasons) for domestic food waste by collecting data from 384 households of Mangalore District of Karnataka and also to find out the solution/ suggestions to reduce or reuse food waste at domestic level of the study area.

Keywords: food waste, domestic level, route, suggestions.

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Introduction

Food is considered as any materials which is best to consume by the creatures of the universe for their survival. Food is generated from plants and animals. Food provides nutrition to the body. The food which is generated from plant is termed as vegetarian and from animals is termed as non vegetarian. Food waste is considered as the wastage of the edible and non-edible consumption materials. The edible parts of the plants and animals is cultivated, produced and prepared for human consumption , but it is not consumed by various reasons is treated as “food waste.” Food waste is a universal problem. According FAO of UN, 1.3 billion tons of food produced for human consumption is wasted every year. The food which are fit for human consumption, but which is discarded or unused by the human being either at retail stage or at final consumption. If the final consumer discards the food material before consumption is termed as “domestic food waste.” According to FAO estimates the State of Food Security and Nutrition in world 2017 report , 190.7 million people are undernourished in India. This represents 14.5% of the Indian population. UN estimates, nearly 40% of the food produced in

India is wasted or lost and this cost one lakh crore rupees in India ever year. Food waste in India happens at every stage , i.e., cultivation, harvesting, carriage, processing, packaging, consumption(domestic) . Proper importance must be given to the domestic food waste management and it should be considered as the need of the hour. This paper concentrated on domestic food waste management.

Objective of the study

1. To identify the predominant reasons for food waste at household level.
2. To provide possible suggestion to reduce or reuse of food waste at domestic level

Limitations of the study

Waste is of different forms like solid waste, liquid waste, industrial waste, domestic waste, agricultural waste, e-waste, medicine waste, biodegradable waste and more. This research paper concentrated only on domestic food waste management. Domestic solid waste and liquid waste aspect is not considered for the study.

Research methods

This paper is based on primary data collected from 384 households in Mangalore region of Karnataka. The collected data has been analyzed using Garate technique to evaluate the constraints associated with reuse of food and reduce the wastage of food. A structured questionnaire was designed, which focused on the objectives of the study. Secondary information was sourced from research papers from research scholar and research gate, journals, book and magazines.

Literature review:

Lasaridi, K., et al (2014) the research result indicated that the people's reaction towards the prevention of food waste at the household level is positive. They have better practice towards reducing and reusing food waste at their respective houses, i.e, most of the respondents are very cautious while purchasing perishable food items. The positive attitude is strongly influenced by the severe recession experienced by the people in the Greek, which made the people more careful in their expenditures. the result may act as a yardstick to further establish a food waste prevention behaviour at household level on the basis of environmental and social awareness , that may outlast the economic crisis.

Lamberton et al (2016) the study focused on the waste that generate from the households behaviour and attitude from the first stage of purchasing the food material till the last stage of disposal of food waste. The author set forth a behavioural theory based to explain food waste in squander sequence to encourage the future research in that particular area.

Simona Romani et al (2018) , the study examines the extent to which the household consumers food management behaviour results in huge food waste and identifies that understanding of that attitude of the consumers and helps to find the possible ways to reduce food waste at the household level for the benefit of everyone.

Discussion

Generally the reasons for domestic food waste of people would differ from one to another. In order to understand the attitude of the respondents, the respondents were asked to rank following common and

popular reasons for domestic food waste by assigning ranks system. Most prominent reason is given rank 1, next 2.....like the last is 11.

Table 1

Ranking of the reasons for domestic food waste by the respondents

Reasons for domestic food waste	Rank given by the Respondents											Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
1 BB	58	92	35	23	15	42	19	32	12	21	35	384
2 HE	92	52	35	42	55	12	16	30	25	19	06	384
3 PMP	23	20	15	42	60	22	53	43	52	22	32	384
4 POSFC	37	26	19	33	25	39	28	34	57	38	48	384
5 NEFCC	12	52	41	63	19	28	46	23	42	32	26	384
6 PN	73	40	35	22	10	42	51	36	29	27	19	384
7 DTPHM	12	22	28	42	51	35	28	52	49	22	43	384
8 DS	22	32	62	46	66	61	33	29	22	07	04	384
9 LCPF	09	12	24	31	39	42	61	58	12	52	44	384
10 LKFRM	24	20	43	21	24	42	35	32	35	46	62	384
11 BNED	22	16	47	19	20	19	14	15	49	98	65	384

Source: Field Survey

Where 1: (BB) Blind Belief

Where 2: (HE) Health effects (not to consume yesterday's food)

Where 3: (PMP) No proper meal plan

Where 4: (POSFC) Preference towards outside food consumption

Where 5: (NEFCC) Non edible food can't be consumed

Where 6: (PN) Perishable in nature (can't preserve for long)

Where 7: (DTPHM) Different taste and preferences of household members

Where 8: (DS) Discount offered by supermarket made consumers to buy in bulk

Where 9: (LCPF) Lack of concentration while preparing food

Where 10: (LKFRM) Lack of knowledge about food reuse methods

Where 11: (BNED) Buying the things which are near to expiry dates

Total number of respondents 384

To find out the most significant and popular reasons for domestic food waste of the respondents; Garrett's ranking technique was used. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the

rank for all the reasons for domestic food waste and the outcome of such ranking has been converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percent position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_{ij}}$$

With the help of Garrett's ranking technique, the percent position estimated is converted into scores. Then for each reason for domestic food waste, the scores of each individual are added and then total value of scores and mean values of score is calculated. The reasons for domestic food waste having highest mean value is considered to be the most important reason for domestic food waste.

Table 2
Calculation of Garret Value

S. No.	100 (R _{ij} - 0.5)/ N _{ij}	Calculated value	Garret Value
1.	100 (1 - 0.5) / 11	4.55	83
2.	100 (2 - 0.5) / 11	13.66	72
3.	100 (3 - 0.5) / 11	22.77	65
4.	100 (4 - 0.5) / 11	31.82	59
5.	100 (5 - 0.5) / 11	40.91	55
6.	100 (6 - 0.5) / 11	50.00	50
7.	100 (7 - 0.5) / 11	59.09	45
8.	100 (8 - 0.5) / 11	68.18	41
9.	100 (9 - 0.5) / 11	77.27	35
10.	100 (10 - 0.5) / 11	86.36	28
11.	100 (11 - 0.5) / 11	95.45	18

Source: Field Survey

Table 3
Calculation of Garret Value for the prominent reasons for domestic food waste by the respondents

G Value	83	72	65	59	55	50	45	41	35	28	18
Ranks	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 BB	4814	6624	2275	1357	825	2100	855	1312	420	588	630
2 HE	7636	3744	2275	2478	3025	600	720	1230	875	532	108
3 PMP	1909	1440	975	2478	3300	1100	2385	1763	1820	616	576
4 POSFC	3071	1872	1235	1947	1375	1950	1260	1394	1995	1064	864
5 NEFCC	996	3744	2665	3717	1045	1400	2070	943	1470	896	468
6 PN	6059	2880	2275	1298	550	2100	2295	1476	1015	756	342
7 DTPHM	996	1584	1820	2478	2805	1750	1260	2132	1715	616	774
8 DS	1826	2304	4030	2714	3630	3050	1485	1189	770	196	72

9 LCPF	747	864	1560	1829	2145	2100	2745	2378	420	1456	792
10 LKFRM	1992	1440	2795	1239	1320	2100	1575	1312	1225	1288	1116
11 BNED	1826	1152	3055	1121	1100	950	630	615	1715	2744	1170

Source: Field Survey

Table 4

Ranking of prominent reasons for domestic food waste by the respondents

S. No.	Reasons for domestic food waste	Total	Per cent	Rank
1.	1 BB	21800	56.77	2
2.	2 HE	23223	60.48	1
3.	3 PMP	18362	47.82	6
4.	4 POSFC	18027	46.95	7
5.	5 NEFCC	19414	50.56	5
6.	6 PN	21046	54.81	4
7.	7 DTPHM	17930	46.69	8
8.	8 DS	21266	55.38	3
9.	9 LCPF	17036	44.36	10
10.	10 LKFRM	17402	45.32	9
11.	11 BNED	16078	41.87	11

Source: Field Survey

It is evidence from the Table 4 that the prominent reasons for domestic food waste by the respondents in the study area are Health effects (not to consume yesterday's food - 60.48) followed by Blind Belief (56.77), Discount offered by supermarket made consumers to buy in bulk (55.38), Perishable in nature (can't preserve for long - 54.81), Non edible food can't be consumed (50.56), No proper meal plan (47.82), Preference towards outside food consumption (46.95), Different taste and preferences of household members (46.69), Lack of knowledge about food reuse methods (45.32), Lack of concentration while preparing food (44.36) and the least importance is given to Buying the things which are near to expiry dates (41.87).

Suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level

The study further analysed the measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level to understand the perception of the respondents. The respondents were asked to rank the following common and popular measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level by assigning ranks system. Most prominent measures or suggestion is given rank 1, next 2.....like the last is 8.

Table 5

Ranking of the suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level by the respondents

Measures or Suggestion	Rank given by the Respondents								Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
Proper meal plan	58	59	72	45	42	31	46	31	384
Pet animal	32	22	45	85	72	75	25	28	384
Food waste composting system	26	63	62	59	48	43	46	37	384
First in first out while using	82	64	56	43	48	52	25	14	384
Buying in small quantity *	42	37	62	48	46	57	63	29	384
Purchase by considering expiry date	52	42	28	32	52	46	70	62	384
Innovative methods **	69	65	34	36	19	11	75	75	384
Donate the excess food to the needy	23	32	25	36	57	69	34	108	384

Source: Field Survey

* Buying in small quantity means not to buy the perishable things in bulk

** Innovative methods means Innovative methods of reusing yesterday's food

Total number of respondents 384

To find out the most significant measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level; Garrett's ranking technique was used. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all the measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level and the outcome of such ranking has been converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Per cent position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_{ij}}$$

With the help of Garrett's ranking technique, the per cent position estimated is converted into scores. Then for each measure or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level, the scores of each individual are added and then total value of scores and mean values of score is calculated. The measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level having highest mean value is considered to be the most significant measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level.

Table 6

Calculation of Garret Value

S. No.	100 (R _{ij} - 0.5)/ N _{ij}	Calculated value	Garret Value
1.	100 (1 - 0.5) / 8	6.25	80
2.	100 (2 - 0.5) / 8	18.75	67
3.	100 (3 - 0.5) / 8	31.25	60
4.	100 (4 - 0.5) / 8	43.75	53
5.	100 (5 - 0.5) / 8	56.25	47
6.	100 (6 - 0.5) / 8	68.75	41
7.	100 (7 - 0.5) / 8	81.25	32
8.	100 (8 - 0.5) / 8	93.75	20

Source: Field Survey

Table 7

Calculation of Garret Value for the prominent measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level by the respondents

Garret Value	80	67	60	53	47	41	32	20
Ranks	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Proper meal plan	4640	3953	4320	2385	1974	1271	1472	620
Pet animal	2560	1474	2700	4505	3384	3075	800	560
Food waste composting system	2080	4221	3720	3127	2256	1763	1472	740
First in first out while using	6560	4288	3360	2279	2256	2132	800	280
Buying in small quantity*	3360	2479	3720	2544	2162	2337	2016	580
Purchase by considering expiry date	4160	2814	1680	1696	2444	1886	2240	1240
Innovative methods **	5440	4355	2040	1908	893	451	2400	1500
Donate the excess food to the needy	1840	2144	1500	1908	2679	2829	1088	2160

Source: Field Survey

Table 8

Ranking of prominent measures or suggestion to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level by the respondents

S. No.	Reasons for domestic food waste	Total	Per cent	Rank
1.	Proper meal plan	20635	53.74	2
2.	Pet animal	19058	49.63	5
3.	Food waste composting system	19379	50.47	3
4.	First in first out while using	21955	57.17	1
5.	Buying in small quantity *	19198	49.99	4
6.	Purchase by considering expiry date	18160	47.29	7
7.	Innovative methods **	18987	49.45	6
8.	Donate the excess food to the needy	16148	42.05	8

Source: Field Survey

It is evidence from the Table 8 that the prominent measures or suggestions to reduce/ reuse food waste at domestic level in the study area are First in first out of consumable items system of usage (57.17) followed by making a proper meal plan (53.74), introduction of food waste composting system (50.47), Buying in small quantity means not to buy the perishable things in bulk(49.99), feeding Pet animals(49.63), Innovative methods means Innovative methods of reusing yesterday's food(49.45), Purchase by considering expiry date (47.29) and the least importance is given to Donate the excess food to the needy (42.05).

Conclusion

The study concludes that , adverse effect on health is the major reason towards wastage of food at domestic level followed by blind belief of the people and the huge discounts offered by the super markets. Food waste can be controlled by following various precautionary measures, i.e, following First In First Out system while using food items followed by making proper meal plan so that adverse

effect on health can be avoided and making food composting at domestic level etc. Waste is the thing which can be abolished completely but it can be avoided or renovated by following proper measures in day to day life.

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